

Counting Electrons on Supported Nanoparticles

Yaroslava Lykhach^{1,†}, Sergey M. Kozlov^{2,†}, Tomáš Skála³, Andrii Tovt³, Vitalii Stetsovych³, Nataliya Tsud³, Filip Dvořák³, Viktor Johánek³, Armin Neitzel¹, Josef Mysliveček³, Stefano Fabris⁴, Vladimír Matolín³, Konstantin M. Neyman,^{2,5,‡} Jörg Libuda^{1,6*}

Subject terms: Electron transfer; Heterogeneous catalysis; Nanoparticles; Electronic properties and materials; Nanoscale materials; Surfaces, interfaces and thin films;

¹Lehrstuhl für Physikalische Chemie II, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Egerlandstraße 3, D-91058 Erlangen, Germany

²Departament de Química Física and Institut de Química Teòrica i Computacional (IQTCUB), Universitat de Barcelona, c/ Martí i Franquès 1, 08028 Barcelona, Spain

³Charles University, Faculty of Mathematics and Physics, Department of Plasma and Surface Science, V Holešovičkách 2, 18000 Prague 8, Czech Republic

⁴CNR-IOM DEMOCRITOS, Istituto Officina dei Materiali, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche and SISSA, Via Bonomea 265, I-34136, Trieste, Italy

⁵Institució Catalana de Recerca i Estudis Avançats (ICREA), 08028 Barcelona, Spain

⁶Erlangen Catalysis Resource Center, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Egerlandstraße 3, D-91058 Erlangen, Germany

Keywords: electronic metal support interaction, ceria, platinum, supported metal catalyst, photoelectron spectroscopy, scanning tunneling microscopy, density functional calculations

[†] These authors contributed equally to the work and should both be regarded as first author.

[‡] To whom correspondence should be addressed. FAX: +34 93 402 1231, email: konstantin.neyman@icrea.cat

* To whom correspondence should be addressed. FAX: +49 9131 8528867, email: joerg.libuda@fau.de

Electronic interactions between metal nanoparticles and oxide supports control the functionality of nanomaterials, for example, the stability, the activity, and the selectivity of catalysts.¹⁻⁵ Such interactions involve electron transfer across the metal/support interface. In this work we quantify this charge transfer on a well-defined platinum/ceria catalyst at particle sizes relevant for heterogeneous catalysis. Combining synchrotron-radiation photoelectron spectroscopy, scanning tunneling microscopy, and density functional calculations we show that the charge transfer per Pt atom is largest for Pt particles of around 50 atoms. Here, approximately 1 electron is transferred per 10 Pt atoms from the nanoparticle to the support. For larger particles, the charge transfer reaches its intrinsic limit set by the support. For smaller particles charge transfer is partially suppressed by nucleation at defects. These mechanistic and quantitative insights into charge transfer will help to make better use of particle size effects and electronic metal support interactions in metal/oxide nanomaterials.

Complex nanomaterials play an ever growing role in numerous key technologies. For instance, noble metal nanoparticles on oxides are among the most common catalytic materials,⁶ with many applications in chemical industry, fuel production, environmental catalysis, photocatalysis, and electrocatalysis.^{5,7-10} Efficient use of the precious metals in these materials is essential for cost-efficient catalytic processes. Strategies to improve the activity often rely on particle-support interactions, which are optimized by choosing specific support materials, particle sizes, particle structures, or by adding promoters.^{1,3-5}

For more than 30 years, particle-support interactions have been among the most intensively and most controversially discussed topics in catalysis.^{2,7} Today, we understand that the catalytic activity of supported nanoparticles is governed by several interrelated physical and chemical

factors, such as their electronic structure,⁸ their nanostructure,^{1,4} their structural flexibility^{11,12} and, very importantly, their interaction with the support.^{5,9,13-15} Understanding these phenomena is the key to tailor-made materials and has been attracting the attention of many physicists, chemists and materials engineers.

The outstanding influence of reducible supports on the activity of metal nanoparticles is well known since the discovery of the “strong metal support interaction” (SMSI) by Tauster et al. in the late 1970’s.¹⁴ Recently, Rodriguez, Illas and co-workers identified a different kind of strong metal-support interaction for a Pt/ceria catalyst, which did not lead to a decrease in activity typical for the “classical” SMSI effect but to a 20-fold increase in the rate for the water-gas shift reaction.⁴ A strong electronic interaction between Pt particles and the support is proposed to be at the origin of the effect. Campbell suggested to use the term Electronic Metal Support Interaction (EMSI) for this type of chemical enhancement,² which also attracted a lot of attention from theory.¹⁶ On the one hand the effect will dramatically change the catalytic properties of the metal particle.^{1,17} On the other hand such interactions are critical for the adhesion of particles and, therefore, for the stability of the material.¹⁸

Depending on the magnitude of the EMSI there will be substantial charge transfer (CT) between the supported metal particle and the supporting oxide. Qualitatively, this CT was observed by many groups (see e.g. ^{19,20}) but, surprisingly, the amount of CT was never quantified for supported metal particles in the catalytically relevant size range.

In fact, measuring the CT between a supported catalyst particle and the support turns out to be a serious challenge. Attempts can be traced back throughout the history of surface science and model catalysis.^{16,21,22} In principle, the charge on a supported particle could be determined from binding energy (BE) shifts in photoelectron spectroscopy (PES). In practice, however, strong

final state effects prevent reliable measurements of the small initial state effects due to EMSI.²³⁻
²⁵ Recently, Niluis *et al.* determined the charge on oxide-supported Au and Pd adatoms and clusters by scanning tunneling microscopy (STM),^{21,26} but this method is restricted to very small aggregates only. To the best of our knowledge, the charge on supported nanoparticles in the nanometer size regime has not been measured to date.

To address this challenge we study Pt particles supported on cerium oxide, a versatile heterogeneous catalyst with applications in hydrogen production, reforming, environmental catalysis, and electrocatalysis.¹⁰ Upon contact of the Pt metal with the oxide surface, the EMSI leads to electron transfer across the metal/oxide interface.^{4,9} These electrons are taken up by Ce⁴⁺ ions at the interface which, thereby, are reduced to Ce³⁺. The Ce³⁺ centers can be detected with outstanding sensitivity by resonant photoemission spectroscopy (RPES).⁵ Noteworthy RPES allows detection of Ce³⁺ down to surface concentration levels of 0.1% and below. Combining this information with structural data from STM, we are able to “count” the number of electrons transferred across the metal/oxide interface per Pt particle. Specifically, we can measure the CT as a function of particle size, from very small aggregates to particles containing several hundreds of atoms.

In our experiments we start from a well-ordered and well-characterized CeO₂(111) film grown on a Cu(111) single crystal under ultrahigh vacuum conditions (see Methods).^{23,27} We choose a relatively high film thickness of about 2 nm to minimize the influence of the underlying Cu substrate. Further, we used preparation conditions, which yield a nearly perfectly stoichiometric oxide (CeO_{1.998 ± 0.001}, as determined from RPES, see below). On this stoichiometric film we can also exclude particle-induced segregation of oxygen vacancies which was discussed recently.^{18,28} Onto this surface we deposited Pt by physical vapor deposition (PVD). The deposition rate was

calibrated by XPS and high resolution Pt 4f spectra were recorded by means of synchrotron radiation (Figure 1). These spectra reveal the typical shift to higher BE with decreasing particle size largely dominated by the final state Coulomb charge in the photoemission process.²³ As pointed out, it is not possible to determine reliably the initial state CT from these spectra.

The particle density, size, and shape were investigated by STM, which was combined in-situ with XPS to correlate the structural data and the Pt coverage. Whereas tip convolution effects make it difficult to extract particle sizes directly from STM, the particle density can be determined with very good precision. From the particle density and the coverage calibration from XPS (see Supplementary Information), we are able to obtain reliable information on the average number of Pt atoms per nanoparticle. Average particle sizes can then be estimated using the particle shape from STM in the limit of larger metal loading where this data is more reliable. Particle densities and sizes from this structural analysis are summarized in Figure 1 as a function of Pt coverage. We clearly identify the regions of nucleation, particle growth and coalescence, as is typically observed for such systems. The data shows that we can vary the particle size from approximately 20 to 800 Pt atoms per particle, corresponding to particle diameters between about 1 and 3.5 nm. This is a common size regime for Pt particles in heterogeneous catalysis.

Next we use this model catalyst to determine the CT between the supported particles and the oxide by RPES. Briefly, the method is based on valence band photoelectron spectroscopy at photon energies that lead to resonant enhancement of features associated either with Ce³⁺ or Ce⁴⁺.^{5,29} From these resonant enhancements we derive the surface concentration of Ce³⁺ by calibration with conventional PES (see Supplementary Information for details). Using this procedure we are able to quantitatively measure the Ce³⁺ concentration and, thereby, “count” the number of electrons that are transferred between the Pt particles and the ceria support.

The results are summarized in Figure 2. Three important quantities are displayed as a function of particle size: the number of electrons transferred per Pt particle, the number of electrons transferred per Pt atom and the number of electrons transferred per surface area. We observe that the number of electrons transferred per particle linearly increases with size for particles with up to 70 Pt atoms. For larger particles further charge transfer is suppressed. Interestingly, the charge per Pt atom shows a maximum at particle sizes between 30 and 70 Pt atoms (particle diameters between approximately 1 and 1.5 nm). Here, it reaches a peak value of about 0.11 ± 0.025 electrons per Pt atom. In other words, the Pt nanoparticles become partially oxidized, forming $\text{Pt}^{\delta+}$ with an average charge of $\delta \sim 0.11 \pm 0.025$ (The error margin mainly originates from potential shadowing effects and the calibration procedure; see Supplementary Information for details. Note that the appearance of the CT maximum does not depend on the calibration procedure).

At higher Pt coverage the overall number of transferred electrons approaches a limit. The maximum CT per surface area amounts to 1.2×10^{18} electrons/m². This value corresponds to approximately 17% of the surface cerium ions being reduced to Ce^{3+} . We conclude that on average 1 out of 6 Ce^{4+} surface ions can be reduced to Ce^{3+} . Beyond this value no further charge transfer occurs and the average charge per Pt atom decreases if additional Pt is deposited. Interestingly, the CT per Pt atom also decreases for very small aggregates. This observation is surprising as theory predicts substantial CT even for very small aggregates.⁵ Below we will show that the suppressed CT may be explained by nucleation of Pt at Ce^{3+} defect sites. Traces of Ce^{3+} present at the pristine surface (0.5% ML) are sufficient to account for the observed effect. Previous studies have shown that these Ce^{3+} centers may serve as efficient traps for deposited metal atoms.³⁰

To rationalize the experimental observations we have performed systematic density functional calculations (see Methods). Using CeO₂(111)-supported Pt nanoparticle models we explore the influence of the particle size, of the particle density and of oxygen vacancies. Whereas many different particle sizes and structures coexist in the experiment, theoretical models are restricted to few selected systems. Therefore, theory can only rationalize the experimental trends rather than reproduce the experimental data quantitatively.

To explore the effect of particle size, we calculate Pt₈, Pt₃₄, and Pt₉₅ particles on CeO₂(111) (see Figure 3 and Supplementary Information for details). For each model we were able to identify several configurations of similar energy corresponding to different numbers of electrons transferred. In practice such configurations coexist and indicate the range in which electron transfer is possible. For the Pt₈ cluster we find the transfer of 1-2 electrons from Pt₈ to CeO₂(111), for Pt₃₄ the transfer of 1-3 electrons is possible, and for Pt₉₅ even 4-6 electrons can be transferred. This results in a partial charge Pt^{δ+} of $\delta = 0.13-0.25$ for Pt₈, of $\delta = 0.03-0.09$ for Pt₃₄, and $\delta = 0.04-0.06$ for Pt₉₅. In spite of the simplicity of the model the amount of charge transfer compares well with the experimental value of $\delta = 0.11 \pm 0.025$ for particle sizes between 30 and 70 atoms. Note that the decreasing partial charge for larger particles is also reproduced in the model.

A second observation in the experiments is that the fraction of surface Ce³⁺ centers does not exceed a value of ~17%. This number also compares well with the simulations. For the Pt₃₄ cluster on a p(4×4) CeO₂(111) supercell, we calculate a fraction of 6-19 % Ce³⁺, whereas for Pt₉₅ on a p(5×5) CeO₂(111) supercell, we obtain values of 16-24 % Ce³⁺. To explore possible limitations for CT caused by the concentration of surface Ce³⁺ centers we varied the density of Pt₈ clusters on surface. When two particles are placed on a p(4×4) supercell only 2 Ce⁴⁺ cations

are reduced to Ce^{3+} , the same number as for a single particle in the same cell. If the spatial constraint is released by placing the two particles on a larger $p(5\times 5)$ supercell the CT increases to 2-5 electrons. Hence, the electrostatic destabilization at high surface concentrations of Ce^{3+} appears to be limiting the maximum CT.

To explore the origin of the suppressed CT on very small particles, we investigated the influence of O vacancy sites. In fact, vacancies are found to reduce the net charge transfer to ceria: For example, the number of donated electrons decreases from 1–3 to 1–2 for Pt_{34} and from 4–6 to 1–4 for Pt_{95} . The reason is the lower propensity of the partially reduced ceria to accept additional electrons. Therefore, we attribute the lower CT on small clusters to nucleation at defects of the CeO_2 surface.

Finally, our calculations suggest that the CT can have a substantial influence on adsorption and, therefore, on reactivity. For instance, the CT can strengthen the adsorption of CO and H_2O by as much as 0.5 eV, whereas the effect on adsorbed oxygen is negligible (see Supplementary Information). This illustrates the CT effect can be very important but its specific role has to be analyzed individually for each reaction system.

In summary, we have quantified the CT between supported Pt nanoparticles and a well-defined ceria support that occurs as a result of the electronic metal support interaction. We show that the CT reveals a characteristic size dependence and reaches a maximum for particles between 30 and 70 atoms, where up to 0.11 electrons are transferred per Pt atom ($\text{Pt}^{\delta+}$ with $\delta \approx 0.11$). For smaller particles, nucleation at defects hinders the CT whereas the support limits the CT for larger particles. These results show that the CT can be tuned by adjusting the particle size, the structure and by the chemical properties of the support. Whereas for large particles the charge will be mainly localized at metal atoms in the vicinity of the interface, small aggregates close to the CT

maximum consist of few atomic layers only. Therefore, most of their surface atoms will bear an excess charge, an effect that may be used to modify material properties at a knowledge-driven basis.

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Acknowledgments

This work was financially supported by the European Community (FP7-NMP.2012.1.1-1 project ChipCAT, Reference No. 310191), by the “Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft” (DFG) within the Excellence Cluster “Engineering of Advanced Materials” in the framework of the excellence initiative, by Spanish MINECO (grant CTQ2012-34969), by the Generalitat de Catalunya (grants 2014SGR97 and XRQTC), and by the Czech Science Foundation (grant 15-06759S). The authors also acknowledge the CERIC-ERIC Consortium for the access to experimental facilities and financial support and the COST Action CM1104 for additional support. Computer resources and assistance were provided by the Red Española de Supercomputación. S.M.K. is thankful to Spanish Ministerio de Educación for a pre-doctoral FPU Grant AP2009-3379. The authors thank Andre Kaftan for his contribution to the numerical analysis procedure for XPS.

Author contributions

S.M.K. performed the DF calculations. S.M.K., S.F., and K.M.N. analyzed the calculated data and were involved in the preparation of the manuscript. K.M.N. supervised the theoretical work. Y.L., T.S., and N.T. performed the RPES experiments. Y.L., T.S., A.N. and J.L. were involved in the analysis of the experimental data and the preparation of the manuscript. J.L. and V.M. supervised the experimental work. A.T., V.S., F.D. V.J., and J.M. performed STM and XPS experiments.

Competing financial interests

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

Methods

Spectroscopic characterisation

High-resolution synchrotron radiation photoelectron spectroscopy (SRPES) and resonant photoemission spectroscopy (RPES) studies were performed at the Materials Science Beamline (MSB), Elettra synchrotron light facility in Trieste, Italy. The MSB, with a bending magnet source, provides synchrotron light in the energy range of 21-1000 eV. The UHV end-station (base-pressure 1×10^{-10} mbar) was equipped with a multichannel electron energy analyzer (Specs Phoibos 150), a rear view Low Energy Electron Diffraction (LEED) optics, an argon sputter gun, and a gas inlet system. The basic setup of the chamber includes a dual Mg/Al x-ray source. Additionally, two electron-beam evaporators for Ce and Pt deposition were installed.

A single crystal Cu(111) disc (MaTecK GmbH, 99.999 %) was used as a substrate for the preparation of the CeO₂(111) films. Cu(111) was cleaned by several cycles of Ar⁺ sputtering (300 K, 60 min) and annealing (723 K, 5 min) until no traces of carbon or any other contaminant were found in the photoelectron spectra. Epitaxial CeO₂(111) films were prepared by Physical Vapor Deposition (PVD) of Ce metal (Goodfellow, 99.99 %) from an electron beam evaporator (Tetra e-flux) in an oxygen atmosphere ($p_{O_2} = 5 \times 10^{-7}$ mbar, Linde, 99.999 %) at 523 K, followed by annealing of the films at 523 K in an oxygen atmosphere at the same pressure for 5 min. The preparation method³¹ yielded a continuous,³² stoichiometric CeO₂(111) film with a thickness of 2.1 nm as determined from the attenuation of the Cu 2p_{3/2} intensity. Low energy

(LEED) and reflection high energy (RHEED) electron diffraction studies of the prepared films confirmed the epitaxial growth of CeO₂(111) with the characteristic (1.5×1.5) superstructure relative to the Cu(111) substrate.

Pt (Goodfellow, 99.99%) was deposited by PVD from an electron beam evaporator (Oxford Scientific OS-Vap) onto the CeO₂(111)/Cu(111) at 300 K. In order to maintain a constant deposition rate of Pt, the evaporator was kept at working parameters with a shutter closed for 5 min before each deposition step. The nominal thickness of the deposited Pt layer was calculated from the attenuation of Cu 2p_{3/2} intensity under the assumption of a 3d growth model for Pt nanoparticles on CeO₂(111) (see Supplementary Information for details).

Core level spectra of Pt 4f, C 1s, and O 1s were acquired at 180, 410, and 650 eV, respectively. The binding energies in the spectra acquired with synchrotron radiation were calibrated with respect to the Fermi level. Additionally, Al K α radiation (1486.6 eV) was used to measure O 1s, Ce 3d, and Cu 2p_{3/2} core levels. All spectra were acquired at constant pass energy and at an emission angle for the photoelectrons of 20° or 0° with respect to the sample normal, while using the X-ray source or synchrotron radiation, respectively.

Valence band spectra were acquired at three different photon energies, 121.4, 124.8, and 115.0 eV, that correspond to the resonant enhancements in Ce³⁺, Ce⁴⁺ ions, and to off-resonance conditions, respectively. Analysis of the spectra obtained with these photon energies forms the basis of RPES. The Ce³⁺ resonance at a photon energy of 121.4 eV is caused by a Super-Coster-Kronig decay involving electron emission from Ce 4f states located about 1.4 eV below the Fermi edge. The Ce⁴⁺ resonance at a photon energy of 124.8 eV involves emission of O 2p electrons (hybridized with Ce states) from the valence band around 4.0 eV. The valence band spectrum measured at a photon energy of 115 eV is used as a background for the calculation of

the intensity difference of the features in on- and off-resonance, denoted as the resonant enhancements for Ce^{3+} , $D(\text{Ce}^{3+})$, and for Ce^{4+} , $D(\text{Ce}^{4+})$, respectively. The resonant enhancement ratio (RER), calculated as $D(\text{Ce}^{3+})/D(\text{Ce}^{4+})$, is the direct measure of the degree of reduction of cerium oxide.

The values of total spectral resolution were 1 eV (Al $K\alpha$), 200 meV ($h\nu = 115 - 180$ eV), 400 meV ($h\nu = 410$ eV), and 650 meV ($h\nu = 650$ eV).

During the experiment, the sample temperature was controlled by a DC power supply passing a current through Ta wires holding the sample. The temperature was monitored by a K-type thermocouple attached to the back of the sample.

Scanning Tunneling Microscopy and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy

The STM/XPS experiments were performed at Charles University in Prague. The UHV setup (base pressure of 10^{-10} mbar) was equipped with STM system, a dual Mg/Al x-ray source, a hemispherical electron energy analyzer (Specs Phoibos 150), a LEED optics, and two electron beam evaporators for depositing Ce and Pt metals. Pt was deposited on a well-ordered $\text{CeO}_2(111)$ film grown on Cu(111) according to the procedure described for SRPES study.

STM images were acquired with commercial Pt-Ir tips (Unisoku). The imaging of $\text{CeO}_2(111)$ and Pt/ $\text{CeO}_2(111)$ films was performed via unoccupied states applying positive sample voltage with respect to the tip. We used sample voltages 2.5 - 3.5 V, and tunneling currents 25 - 75 pA.

Density Functional Calculations

Periodic density functional calculations were carried out using the VASP^{33,34} package and employing the Perdew-Wang³⁵⁻³⁷ (PW91) implementation of the generalized gradient

approximation (GGA) for the exchange-correlation functional. An effective on-site Hubbard correction $U_{\text{eff}} = 4 \text{ eV}$ ^{38,39} was applied to the Ce 4f orbitals within the GGA+U scheme (PW91+4 approximation).^{40,41} A plane-wave basis with the 415 eV cut-off for the kinetic energy and projector-augmented wave⁴² description of core-valence electron interactions were employed. Total energies were converged within 10^{-5} eV. The structures were optimized until forces on relaxed atoms became less than 0.2 eV/nm. Dimensions of the periodic p(4×4) and p(5×5) CeO₂(111) surface cells were 15.27×15.27 nm² and 19.09×19.09 nm², respectively, with 2.2 nm of vacuum separation between adjacent slabs. In the case of CeO₂(111) with O vacancies, a single vacancy was created in the surface O layer at the perimeter of Pt-ceria interface. Due to the size of the employed cells and mostly ionic nature of bonds in ceria, all calculations were performed at Γ -point in the reciprocal space.

The adhesion energies (E_{adh}) of Pt particles comprising N atoms (Pt_N) to CeO₂(111) were calculated as $E_{\text{adh}}[\text{Pt}_N] = E[\text{Pt}_N] + E[\text{CeO}_2(111)] - E[\text{Pt}_N/\text{CeO}_2(111)]$, where $E[\text{Pt}_N]$ and $E[\text{CeO}_2(111)]$ are the total energies of isolated Pt particle and ceria support, respectively, and $E[\text{Pt}_N/\text{CeO}_2(111)]$ is the total energy of the supported particle.

The present calculations were performed on computational resources of CaesarAugusta (Zaragoza, Spain) and IQTCUB (Barcelona, Spain) and consumed more than 10⁶ CPU hours.

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Figure 1. Structural characterization of the Pt/CeO₂(111) model catalyst: (a) Selected STM images of the surface after the deposition of different amounts of Pt. The corresponding atomic models represent typical Pt particle sizes as determined by STM and XPS (see text for details; blue: platinum, red: oxygen, ivory: cerium). (b) From the STM and XPS data we derive the particle density (red triangles) and size (blue squares). (c) The corresponding Pt 4f spectra obtained by synchrotron radiation PES. The Pt coverage is expressed in monolayers (1 ML = 0.2266 nm).

Figure 2. “Counting” the electrons transferred due to the EMSI: (a) The number of electrons transferred per Pt particle to the ceria support increases with increasing particle size (green squares). The partial charge per Pt atom reaches a maximum for particle with 30 to 70 atoms (yellow circles). Here, the EMSI is largest. (b) At higher Pt coverage the total amount of transferred charge approaches a limit which we denote as the “charge transfer limit” (red squares). The atomic models show schematically the average particle sizes in the different regions.

Figure 3. Summary of density functional calculations: The particle size, the particle density, and the oxygen vacancy density on the support are important factors that control the charge transfer. A detailed description of the computational results is provided in Table S1 (see Supplementary Information).

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